

KO'P O'ZGARUVCHILI FUNKSIYALARNING O'ZGARUVCHILARI YANA FUNKSIYA BO'LADIGAN IFODALAR VA HOSILA UCHUN LAPLAS OPERATORIGA DOIR MISOLLAR

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Annotatsiya: Biz bu maqolada asosan ko'p o'zgaruvchili funksiyalarning differentsiallari, Laplas operatorining ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiyaga tatbiqiga doir misollar hamda murakkab ikki o'zgaruvchili funksiyalarni birdan ortiq hosilalarini ko'rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: funksiya, differensial, oshkormas funksiya, Laplas operatori, gradiyent.

FUNKSIYA O'ZGARUVCHISI YANA FUNKSIYA KO'RINISHIDA BO'LADIGAN FUNKSIYALAR DIFFERENSIALLARI

Bizga ko'p o'zgaruvchili funksiyalarning differentsiallari, ularning xususiy hosilalari ma'lum. Uch o'zgaruvchili funksiyaning differentsiali $u=f(x,y,z)$ funksiya uchun differensial shunday ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi.

$$df = \frac{\delta f}{\delta x_1} dx_1 + \frac{\delta f}{\delta x_2} dx_2 + \frac{\delta f}{\delta x_3} dx_3$$

Bunda berilgan funksiyaning differentsialini topishimiz uchun u funksiya o'z o'zgaruvchisi bo'yicha xususiy hosilaga ega bo'lishi va xususiy hosilaga ega bo'lishi uchun uzluksiz bo'lishi kerak. Endilikda biz berilgan funksiya dagi argumentlarning o'zi ham qandaydir o'zgaruvchi yordamida qatnashishiga doir misol ko'ramiz.

1-MISOL. $u=f(\mu, \delta, \vartheta)$ funksiya berilgan bu yerda $\mu = a_1x + b_1y + c_1z$, $\delta = a_2x + b_2y + c_2z$, $\vartheta = a_3x + b_3y + c_3z$ ga teng bo'lsin. U holda bu funksiyaning birinchi va n -tartibli differentsialini toping.

Bu funksiya uchta o'zgaruvchiga ega bo'lgan funksiya, differentsialini topish uchun uning xususiy hosilalarini topish yetarli, bunda har bir o'zgaruvchi bo'yicha bu funksiyaning xususiy hosilalarini topsak, faqat argumentlarni o'zi qoladi.

$du = f'_1(a_1dx + b_1dy + c_1dz) + f'_2(a_2dx + b_2dy + c_2dz) + f'_3(a_3dx + b_3dy + c_3dz)$ ga teng bo'ladi. Endi bu funksiyaning n -tartibli differentsialini topsak,

$du = dx(a_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} + a_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} + a_3 \frac{\partial}{\partial \vartheta}) + dy(b_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} + b_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} + b_3 \frac{\partial}{\partial \vartheta}) + dz(c_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} + c_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} + c_3 \frac{\partial}{\partial \vartheta}) f(\mu, \delta, \vartheta)$ holatga keltirsak, endi uning n -tartibli differentsiali:

$$d^n u = [dx(a_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} + a_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} + a_3 \frac{\partial}{\partial \vartheta}) + dy(b_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} + b_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} + b_3 \frac{\partial}{\partial \vartheta}) + dz(c_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial \mu} + c_2 \frac{\partial}{\partial \delta} + c_3 \frac{\partial}{\partial \vartheta})]^n f(\mu, \delta, \vartheta) \text{ ko`rinishiga ega bo`ladi.}$$

LAPLAS OPERATORI.

2-MISOL. Bizga $u=f(r)$, $r=\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$ $\Delta u = F(r)$ berilgan bo`lsa, mana shu funksiya uchun Laplas operatori ifodasini tuzing.

Yechish:

$$\Delta u = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} \text{ --berilgan ifodaga Laplas operatori deb ataladi. Bu}$$

funksiya murakkab ko`rinishda berilgani uchun funksiyaning har bir argumenti bo`yicha 1-tartibli va ikkinchi tartibli hosilalarini topib chiqamiz:

$$1. \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = f'(r) \left[\frac{x}{\sqrt{x^2+y^2+z^2}} + \frac{y}{\sqrt{x^2+y^2+z^2}} + \frac{z}{\sqrt{x^2+y^2+z^2}} \right] \text{ ga teng bo`ladi.}$$

$$\Delta u = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} = f''(r) + \frac{y^2+z^2}{\sqrt{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^3}} + \frac{x^2+z^2}{\sqrt{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^3}} + \frac{x^2+y^2}{\sqrt{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^3}} =$$

$$[r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}] = f''(r) + \frac{2f'(r)}{r} \text{ ga teng bo`ladi. Demak bizga berilgan}$$

funksiyaning lopital operatori: $\Delta u = f''(r) + \frac{2f'(r)}{r}$ ga teng ekan.

3-MISOL. Quyidagi ayniyatni isbotlang: $\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$ bunda

$$u = \varphi[x + \tau(y)]$$

Isbot. Isbotlash uchun berilgan ko`rinishdagi hosilalarni topib olamiz.

$$1. \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \varphi'[x + \tau(y)] \quad 2. \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = \varphi'[x + \tau(y)]\tau'(y) \quad 3. \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} = \varphi''[x +$$

$$\tau(y)]\tau'(y)$$

$$4. \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \varphi''[x + \tau(y)] \text{ ga teng bo`ladi. } \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x \partial y} = \varphi'[x + \tau(y)] \cdot (\varphi''[x +$$

$$\tau(y)]\tau'(y)), \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = \varphi''[x + \tau(y)]\tau'(y), \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} = [\varphi'[x + \tau(y)]\tau'(y)] \cdot$$

$\varphi''[x + \tau(y)]$ ga teng chiqadi, demak ayniyat isbotlandi.

Shuningdek, biz yuqorida aytib o`tgan lopital operatorimizni ikki argumentli uch argumentli hamda ko`p argumentli funksiyalarga tatbiq qilsak bo`ladi. Berilayotgan differensial ko`rinishdagi misollarimizning barchasida birinchi navbatda ularning har bir o`zgaruvchisi bo`yicha hosilasini topib olishimiz zarur, funksiya hosilaga ega bo`lishi uchun esa u uzluksiz va biror bir oraliqda aniqlangan bo`lishi zarur hamda yetarlilik shartini bilishimiz talaba qilinadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Azlarov T.X. Mansurov. Matematik analizdan ma'ruzalar 2-qism. O'zbekiston nashriyoti, 1995-yil.
2. Б.П. Демидович. Сборник задач и упражнений по математическому анализу. Москва 1997.
3. Fixtengoltest Matematik analizdan ma'ruzalar 2-tom. 1968.
4. Xudoyberganov G.A.K. Vorisov. X.T. Mansurov. B.A. Shoimqulov Matematik analizdan ma'ruzalar 2-qism. 2010.
5. Г.Е. Шилов. Математический анализ.